

CUSTOMER PREFERENCES ON DALI PROCESSED MEAT PRODUCTS AND THEIR BUYING BEHAVIOR

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ABSTRACT

This study examined customer preferences and buying behavior for DALI processed meat products in 34 DALI (Everyday Grocery) stores in Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines, to improve product quality, customer satisfaction, and brand loyalty. This study was descriptive-correlational. The study described the intended customer base's characteristics and interests and identified key connections and patterns that influenced DALI processed meat product customer preferences and buying behavior using these two methods. This dual focus provided valuable academic and business insights. The study examined socio-economic and demographic profiles, taste, flavor uniformity, packaging, freshness, shelf life, texture, appearance, and supply reliability in 384 respondents. The results showed that most customers were young adults (49.5%), male (56.5%), single (69.8%), Roman Catholic (89.1%), high school graduates (61.5%), and low- to middle-income. These demographics shaped consumption patterns, with younger and lower-income respondents prioritizing affordability, taste, and convenience, and higher-income and educated groups prioritizing health, safety, and product transparency. Most of the customers preferred all product attributes, but taste (mean=3.64) and flavor consistency (mean=3.56) are the most important in determining loyalty and repeat purchases. In addition, customers liked DALI processed meat products' taste. They wanted more DALI processed meat products and more flavors. The freshness, packaging, and availability to build customers trust and satisfaction, while affordability influenced the demand. Among younger and middle-income customers, frequent buying, high willingness to recommend, and emotional brand attachment characterized repeat purchase behavior. Statistical analysis showed that product preferences affect customer buying behavior, highlighting the importance of sensory quality and affordability in loyalty and advocacy. To stay competitive, the study recommended taste consistency, labeling

transparency, and demographic segmentation in marketing strategies. Introduce healthier product variants, develop more DALI processed meat products, and add more flavor to existing products. Also, implementing loyalty programs, strengthening inventory systems, leveraging cultural and religious values in branding, and adopting the proposed strategic recommendations to improve customer acquisition and retention based on market data.

Keywords: *DALI (Everyday Grocery), Processed Meat Products, Customer Preferences, Buying Behavior, Brand Loyalty, Customer Demographics.*

INTRODUCTION

The DALI (Everyday Grocery) stores had been growing in Calamba City, Laguna, and other cities nationwide in the Philippines, and they had influenced the buying behaviors of many customers. Because of this, a growing number of customers had looked to retail chains to satisfy their everyday needs. This move had made DALI's own-brand processed meat products increasingly significant, as they were of consistent quality, affordable in price, and simple to find. At the same time, Johnson et al. (2021) emphasized the importance of understanding customers' preferences and buying behaviors for sustainability and competitiveness. The local and worldwide processed meat sector had been evolving because customers had become more health-conscious, and technology had improved. The studies of de Araujo et al. (2022) and Teixeira & Rodrigues (2021) highlighted that purchase decisions were impacted not just by convenience, affordability, and product quality, but also by growing concerns about health, safety, and transparency. Garmyn (2020) and Innovation Market Insights (2025) stated that factors such as packaging, labeling, and brand image greatly influenced consumer choice and loyalty.

The studies of Hong et al. (2023) and Robinson (2025) showed that sensory characteristics (taste, freshness, and quality consistency) were often more important than brand name or price when it came to acceptance. On the other hand, Hung et al. (2016), Yue et al. (2024), and Teixeira et al. (2024) showed that demographic factors like age, gender, income, and education played a major role in preferences and purchase decisions. Besides these variables, Cardoso (2022) and Sulistia (2022) said that trust and emotional attachment to the brand were important aspects that influenced loyalty and repeat purchases. However, the study found that despite the substantial literature about processed meat products, there had still been a big gap in the research that focused on customers in Calamba City, Laguna, particularly those who purchased DALI processed meat products in the 34 DALI (Everyday Grocery) store branches in Calamba City, Laguna. Local economic conditions, demographic realities, and regional consumer trends that had a direct impact on buying behavior at the community level were often overlooked in national and international research. Moreover, the study was undertaken to improve the understanding of consumers' preferences for DALI processed meat products and their buying behavior in Calamba City.

In conclusion, the study aimed to provide localized insights about DALI processed meat products that other merchants could leverage for customer interaction, marketing

tactics, and product development. The findings were anticipated to offer valuable insights for academic research and practical guidance for businesses, helping companies adapt to evolving customer preferences and remain competitive in the retail market.

Research Questions

The increasing competitiveness of the processed meat products industry highlighted the need for product quality, consistency, and customer loyalty, particularly in the processed meat sector. Local producers such as DALI (Everyday Grocery) had to address diverse customer expectations while ensuring that their products remained reliable, appealing, and accessible in modern trade outlets. Despite the growing demand for processed meat products, questions remained about how socio-economic and demographic factors influenced consumer preferences, repeat purchases, and perceptions of product quality.

This study aimed to determine the socio-economic and demographic profile of respondents and examined their buying behavior toward DALI processed meat products. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-economic and demographic profile of the respondent in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Marital Status;
 - 1.4 Religion;
 - 1.5 Educational Attainment;
 - 1.6 Income bracket?
2. What is the level of preferences among customers on DALI processed meat products in terms of:
 - 2.1 Taste;
 - 2.2 Flavor uniformity;
 - 2.3 Packaging consistency;
 - 2.4 Presentation;
 - 2.5 Product freshness;
 - 2.6 Shelf life;
 - 2.7 Texture, appearance, and physical quality;
 - 2.8 Availability and reliability of supply?
3. What is the level of customer buying behavior among customers of Dali processed meat products in terms of:
 - 3.1 Frequency of purchase;
 - 3.2 Brand Loyalty;
 - 3.3 Product choice;
 - 3.4 Willingness to recommend;
 - 3.5 Emotional connection to the brand?
4. Is there a significant relationship between customer preferences and buying behavior?

5. Does customer preferences on DALI processed meat products influence the buying behavior of the customer?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what strategic recommendations can be developed to improve customer preference and buying behavior toward DALI processed meat products?

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology was employed in the study of customer preferences on DALI processed meat products and their buying behavior at 34 DALI (Everyday Grocery) store branches in Calamba City, Laguna. It outlined the systematic procedures and approaches that were used to ensure the validity, reliability, and rigor of the study. Specifically, this section discussed the research design, population and sampling, research instruments, data-gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

By providing a clear methodological framework, this section established how the study had been conducted, ensuring that the findings were both credible and replicable. The methodology served as the foundation for analyzing the relationship between socio-demographic factors, product attributes, and consumer buying behavior, thereby supporting the research objectives.

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational design, combining two complementary approaches to deliver a thorough overview and an in-depth analysis of the data, following the study of Bierut (2025). The descriptive aspect of the study concentrated on methodically characterizing the participants. The study gathered and showcased comprehensive data regarding their socio-economic and demographic profiles, including factors such as age, marital status, religion, educational level, and income range. Furthermore, it collected insights on what respondents liked concerning different characteristics of DALI processed meat products, such as flavor, packaging, freshness, and accessibility. This section provided a clear overview of the respondents' identities and their preferences.

The correlational component explored the statistical relationships among the identified independent variables, which included socio-economic and demographic characteristics, as well as customer preferences, in relation to the dependent variable, customer buying behavior. The study examined the extent to which variables like age, income, and product preferences influenced behaviors, including purchase frequency, brand loyalty, and the likelihood of recommending the product.

By applying these two methodologies, the study not only described the characteristics and interests of the intended customer base but also identified important connections and patterns that influenced customer preferences and buying behavior related to DALI processed meat products. This dual focus offered significant, valuable insights for both academic understanding and practical business applications.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Calamba City, Laguna, focusing on 34 DALI (Everyday Grocery) store branches that offered DALI processed meat products. Calamba City was known as a highly developed urban center in Southern Luzon, marked by its growing population and active economic setting. The city's diverse and expanding customer base provided a pertinent environment for examining customer preferences on DALI processed meat products and their buying behavior.

Furthermore, Calamba featured a dynamic marketplace, where established brands and local producers competed for the interest of customers. This environment offered an excellent opportunity to examine the effectiveness of DALI processed meat products in terms of customer attraction and reach in the marketplace. The selection of this location was thus strategic, as it provided broad access to a diverse group of consumers and facilitated a valuable understanding of the elements that shaped customer buying behaviors and choices in a genuine, competitive environment.

Sampling Design and Sampling Procedure

The study deliberately selected respondents who met specific criteria aligned with the research objectives. Only customers who had purchased DALI processed meat products from 34 DALI (Everyday Grocery) store branches in Calamba City were included. By focusing on actual buyers, the study ensured that the data collected was grounded in real product experience, thereby producing valid and actionable insights.

Purposive sampling was widely applied in prior studies on consumer preferences and buying behavior to capture authentic perspectives. Cayaban et al. (2023) employed this approach to examine Filipino attitudes toward Korean products, while Diokno and Ramilo (2024) used it to study Pop Mart blind box purchases. These applications demonstrated the effectiveness of purposive sampling in targeting relevant respondents and generating meaningful findings, which reinforced its suitability for the present study.

The sampling procedure was implemented as follows:

- 1. Identification of Study Sites.** All 34 DALI store branches in Calamba City served as the primary sites for respondent recruitment, ensuring coverage of areas with significant customer foot traffic.
- 2. Screening of Respondents.** At each branch, customers were screened through a brief qualifying question to determine whether they had previously purchased DALI processed meat products. Only those who met this criterion were invited to participate.
- 3. Sample Size Determination.** The required sample size was computed using the Raosoft formula at a 95% confidence level, based on the estimated population of

34 DALI store branches in Calamba City. This ensured that the sample was sufficiently representative for statistical analysis.

- 4. Recruitment Method.** Qualified customers were approached in-store by a researcher, with the store manager's assistance, and invited to participate in the survey. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained before data collection.
- 5. Data Collection Period.** Data were gathered over multiple days and across different times to capture a diverse range of respondents, reflecting varied purchasing patterns and demographic backgrounds.

By implementing this purposive sampling strategy, the study ensured that the collected data were both relevant and reliable, providing a robust basis for analyzing customer preferences for DALI processed meat products and their buying behaviors at 34 DALI store branches in Calamba City, Laguna.

Respondents of The Study

The respondents of this research study were customers who had purchased DALI processed meat products from 34 DALI (Every Grocery) store branches located in Calamba City. These individuals represented a diverse segment of local customers who actively participated in the city's modern retail environment, particularly in outlets such as DALI (Everyday Grocery). By focusing on actual buyers, the study ensured that the perspectives gathered reflected genuine experiences, preferences, and buying behaviors for the DALI processed meat products.

Calamba City has a population of 608,000 residents as of 2026. While this data point represents the city's entire population, the study focuses on the accessible population of consumers who purchased DALI processed meat products from 34 DALI store branches located in Calamba. This contextualizes the study within the city's demographic profile, while also guaranteeing that the respondents are directly relevant to the research objective.

To determine how many people should take part in a survey, the researcher used the Raosoft calculator. It considered the total population, margin of error, confidence level, and response distribution. First, it calculated the sample size as if the population were unlimited, then adjusted it for the actual population size. This ensured the survey results were accurate and representative.

Research Instrument

The study employed a structured questionnaire for data collection, organized into three sections. Part I collected socio-economic and demographic details of respondents, such as age, gender, education, and income, enabling analysis of demographic correlations. Part II focused on customer preferences, evaluating attributes such as taste and packaging using a 4-point Likert scale, with ratings indicating varying levels of

preference. Part III examined buying behavior, including purchase frequency and brand loyalty, also using a 4-point Likert scale to gauge habits and emotional connections to products. To ensure accuracy, the questionnaire underwent content validation by experts and pilot testing to refine clarity and effectiveness before final deployment.

Validation and Scoring

To quantify and interpret respondents' perceptions, Figure 1 shows validation and scoring per variable measurement, using the **Likert scale scoring system**. Each item in the questionnaire was assigned a numerical value corresponding to the respondent's level of preference or agreement. This structured scoring method ensures clarity, consistency, and reliability in data interpretation. By translating raw responses into categorical ranges with verbal interpretations, the study can meaningfully evaluate customer preferences and behaviors across different variables.

The survey used a 4-point Likert scale to quantify responses, ensuring all respondents commit to either an agreement or a disagreement stance:

Numerical Rating	Scale Range	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation for Preferences	Verbal Interpretation for Buying Behavior
4	3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Preferred	Very High
3	2.51 – 3.25	Agree	Preferred	High
2	1.76 – 2.50	Disagree	Less Preferred	Low
1	1.00 – 1.75	Very Disagree	Not Preferred	Very Low

Figure 1. Validation and Scoring per Variable Measurement

Statistical Treatment of Data

The survey data were systematically analyzed using appropriate statistical methods to address the research objectives. The following procedures were employed:

- 1. Mean (Averaging):** The mean was used to determine participants' average responses to each questionnaire item, particularly those measured on the 4-point Likert scale. This helped summarize and interpret the central tendency of customer preferences and perceptions regarding DALI-processed meat products.
- 2. Test of Difference:** To assess whether there were statistically significant differences between groups (e.g., based on demographic characteristics such as age, income, or education), appropriate tests of significance, such as the t-test or Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), were employed. These tests determined if

observed differences in customer preferences or buying behaviors were meaningful and not due to random variation.

- 3. Test of Correlation:** To examine the relationships between variables, such as the association between customer preferences and buying behavior, correlation analysis (e.g., Pearson's r) was conducted. This method identified the strength and direction of relationships between independent variables (demographic profile and preferences) and the dependent variable (buying behavior), providing valuable insights into the factors that influenced consumer decisions.
- 4. Test of Normality:** Before conducting parametric statistical tests (e.g., t-test, ANOVA, Pearson's r), the distribution of the data was examined to determine whether it approximated normality. Tests such as the Shapiro-Wilk or Kolmogorov-Smirnov test were applied, alongside graphical methods (e.g., histograms, Q-Q plots). Establishing normality was essential to validate the assumptions underlying parametric analyses. If the data significantly deviated from the normal distribution, appropriate non-parametric alternatives (e.g., Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis test, Spearman's ρ) were considered to ensure the robustness and validity of the findings.

By applying these statistical methods, the study ensured a robust, comprehensive analysis of the data, enabling clear conclusions and actionable recommendations grounded in empirical evidence.

Scope and Limitation of The Study

The study was limited to evaluating customer preferences for DALI processed meat products and their buying behavior among individuals aged 18 years and above who had purchased from 34 DALI (Everyday Grocery) store branches in Calamba City, Laguna. The analysis covered the Academic Year 2025-2026. The study focused on how socio-demographic factors (age, gender, education, income, etc.) and product attributes (taste, flavor, packaging, presentation, freshness, shelf life, texture, appearance, physical quality, availability, and reliability) influenced customer buying decisions, including brand loyalty and purchase frequency. Only individual customers who had purchased DALI processed meat products at the 34 DALI (Everyday Grocery) store branches in Calamba City, Laguna, were considered.

The principal limitation of the study was its focus on a single locality, along with selected demographic and product-related variables. Nonetheless, the study was designed to yield insights that could inform business strategies for enhancing DALI (Everyday Grocery) branches in Calamba City, Laguna. The findings of the study could also serve as a basis for strengthening the local market presence of other DALI (Everyday Grocery) stores located in different municipalities and regions nationwide.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution in Terms of Type of Age.

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage
18-28	190	49.47%
29-38	112	29.16%
39-48	56	14.58%
49-58	15	3.90%
59-69	11	2.86%
TOTAL	384	100.0

Table 1.1 showed that of the 384 respondents, nearly half (49.47%) were aged 18-28, followed by 29.16% aged 29-38, 14.58% aged 39-48, 3.90% aged 49-58, and only 2.86% aged 59-69. This indicates that the study primarily reflected the perspectives of younger adults.

Hung et al. (2016) noted that younger consumers, while frequent buyers of processed meats, are increasingly health-conscious and value clear labeling. Ghaffouli et al. (2025) further supported this by stating that processed meat consumption is generally higher among younger, educated groups, while older adults avoid such products due to health concerns. Yue et al. (2024) added that sensory appeal, especially taste and freshness, is most important to younger, price-sensitive consumers, whereas older individuals prioritize health and sustainability, contributing to their lower representation and engagement.

Table 1.2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution in Terms of Type of Gender.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	167	43.5%
Male	217	56.5%
Prefer Not to Disclose	0	0%
Total	384	100.0

Table 1.2 showed that out of 384 respondents, 56.5% were male (217) and 43.5% were female (167), indicating a slight male majority among DALI processed meat consumers, but with strong female representation as well.

Török et al. (2023) noted that gender, along with age and income, significantly affects consumer preferences, with men possibly being more frequent buyers due to higher consumption or a preference for convenience foods. Yi Bu et al. (2021) found that men often consume more meat-based products, while women may be more health-conscious. Teixeira et al. (2024) added that men tend to prioritize taste and affordability,

whereas women focus more on nutrition and product safety. Overall, these findings suggest that while men form the majority, both genders play important roles in processed meat consumption and influence market trends.

Table 1.3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution in Terms of Type of Marital Status.

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	98	25.5%
Separated	9	2.3%
Single	268	69.8%
Widowed	9	2.3%
Total	384	100.0

Table 1.3 showed that the majority of respondents were single (69.8%), followed by married individuals (25.5%), with smaller proportions separated (2.3%) and widowed (2.3%). This indicates that most DALI processed meat consumers are single, highlighting the importance of convenience and affordability.

Hung et al. (2016) noted that single respondents, though frequent and experimental buyers, are also health-conscious and value clear labeling. Spasova (2024) found that marital status influences responses to advertising, with singles preferring messages focused on independence and lifestyle, while married consumers respond more to social proof and commitment. Teixeira et al. (2024) added that singles tend to prioritize taste, convenience, and affordability, whereas married consumers focus more on nutrition and product safety for their households.

Table 1.4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution in Terms of Type of Religion.

Religion	Frequency	Percentage
Born Again	32	8.3%
Christian	1	0.3%
Christian Baptist	1	0.3%
Iglesia ni Cristo	8	2.1%
Roman Catholic	342	89.1%
Total	384	100.0

Table 1.4 showed that most respondents were Roman Catholic (89.1%), followed by Born Again Christians (8.3%), with small percentages from Iglesia ni Cristo (2.1%), Christian (0.3%), and Christian Baptist (0.3%). This distribution reflects the religious makeup of the local community, with Catholicism dominating.

According to Bolton (2025), religious affiliation influences values, beliefs, and rituals that shape consumer behavior, with Catholic values such as compassion and

stewardship impacting purchasing patterns. Jieqiong et al. (2021) further noted that Catholics tend to prioritize trust, safety, and family values, leading to cautious, value-driven consumption and brand loyalty. Minority groups, meanwhile, may use product choices to express distinct identities, while globalization introduces modern influences alongside traditional religious values.

Table 1.5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution in Terms of Type of Educational Attainment.

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
College Graduate	90	23.5%
Elementary	12	3.1%
High School	236	61.5%
Post Graduate Degree	5	1.3%
Vocational	41	10.7%
Total	384	100.0

Table 1.5 showed that most respondents were high school graduates (61.5%), followed by college graduates (23.5%), those with vocational training (10.7%), elementary graduates (3.1%), and postgraduate degree holders (1.3%). This suggests that DALI processed meat products mainly appeal to the middle educational segment.

Grewal et al. (2022) noted that education influences purchasing decisions, with higher education linked to more informed and responsible buying, while lower education levels are associated with more impulsive choices. Regua (2023) added that high school graduates tend to prioritize affordability and taste, whereas college and vocational graduates focus more on health and product variety. Divya et al. (2025) further emphasized that high school graduates are in a transitional phase, being highly exposed to marketing but still developing critical buying skills, while college graduates are more likely to evaluate product quality and brand trust. Overall, education level was shown to significantly shape consumer preferences and purchasing behavior.

Table 1.6
Frequency and Percentage Distribution in Terms of Type of Monthly Income Bracket.

Monthly Income Bracket	Frequency	Percentage
10,000 - 20,000	136	35.4%
20,001 - 30,000	65	16.9%
30,001 - 40,000	40	10.4%
40,001 - 50,000	12	3.1%
Less than 10,000	111	28.9%
More than 50,000	20	5.2%
Total	384	100.0

Table 1.6 showed that most respondents fell into the ₱10,000-₱20,000 monthly income bracket (35.4%), followed by those earning less than ₱10,000 (28.9%). Other segments included ₱20,001-₱30,000 (16.9%), ₱30,001-₱40,000 (10.4%), ₱40,001-₱50,000 (3.1%), and above ₱50,000 (5.2%). This indicates that the majority are from lower- to middle-income groups, making affordability and value key factors in purchasing DALI processed meat products.

Kaur (2021) found that income directly shapes preferences and demand, with lower-income consumers prioritizing essentials. Abdel Wahab et al. (2023) noted that higher-income consumers are more brand- and fashion-conscious, while lower-income groups are more utilitarian and price-driven. Ahmed et al. (2022) highlighted the role of the middle class (₱20,001-₱40,000, 27.3%) in balancing affordability with aspiration, while the small upper-income group (5.2%) may pursue premium and sustainable products. Overall, income level was shown to significantly influence consumer behavior and product choices.

Table 2.1
Level of Preferences among Customers on DALI Processed Meat Products in Terms of Taste.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. The overall taste of DALI processed meat products is enjoyable. (Ang pangkalahatang lasa ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay masarap.)	3.81	0.44	Highly Preferred
2. The flavor of DALI processed meat products is rich in taste. (Ang lasa ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay malasa.)	3.65	0.52	Highly Preferred
3. The taste of DALI processed meat products is consistent across different brands. (Ang lasa ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay pare-pareho kahit sa iba't ibang brand.)	3.60	0.57	Highly Preferred
4. Compared to fresh meat, DALI processed meat products taste equally enjoyable. (Kung ikukumpara sa sariwang karne, ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay kasing-sarap din kainin.)	3.51	0.57	Highly Preferred
5. Overall, I am satisfied with the taste quality of DALI processed meat products. (Sa kabuuan, ako ay nasisiyahan sa kalidad ng lasa ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI.)	3.65	0.51	Highly Preferred
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.64	0.39	Highly Preferred
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Highly Preferred (HP), 1.75 – 2.49 Less Preferred (LP),	2.50 – 3.24 Preferred (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Preferred (NP)	

Table 2.1 showed that DALI processed meat products received a high overall taste rating, with a mean of 3.64 (Highly Preferred), and customers especially enjoyed the overall flavor (mean of 3.81). Even when compared to fresh meat, DALI products scored

well (mean of 3.51), though some still viewed fresh meat as slightly superior. These findings highlight taste as a key factor in consumer satisfaction and loyalty.

Hong, et al. (2023) and de Araujo et al. (2022) supported this, noting that taste and freshness outweigh brand and price in buying decisions. Sheng et al. (2025) also found taste to be the decisive factor, even as interest in organic products grows. Food Industry Executive (2025) reported that taste and price are the top purchase drivers (81% each), confirming DALI's market strength. However, to further appeal especially to younger consumers, DALI should also focus on ingredient transparency and quality. Overall, taste is a core advantage, but bridging the gap with fresh meat and evolving with consumer preferences will help maintain competitiveness.

Table 2.2
Level of Preferences among Customers on DALI Processed Meat Products in Terms of Flavor.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. The flavor of DALI processed meat products is consistent across bites, reinforcing consumer trust in product consistency. (Ang lasa mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay nagpapakita ng pagiging parepareho ng lasa sa bawat kagat, na nagpapalakas ng tiwala ng mga mamimili sa pareparehong lasa at kalidad ng produkto.)	3.67	0.50	Highly Preferred
2. Regardless of serving condition, the flavor of DALI processed meat products remains steady, reflecting careful production and quality standards. (Anuman ang paraan ng paghahain, nananatiling matatag ang lasa ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI, na sumasalamin sa maingat na pamantayan ng paggawa at kalidad.)	3.53	0.53	Highly Preferred
3. The flavor of DALI processed meat products is consistent when consumed with or without condiments. (Ang lasa ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay nananatiling parepareho kahit kainin nang mayroon o walang sawsawan.)	3.51	0.56	Highly Preferred
4. The flavor of DALI processed meat products does not vary significantly between different pieces of the same product. (Ang lasa ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay hindi gaanong nag-iiba sa bawat piraso ng parehong produkto.)	3.46	0.54	Highly Preferred
5. Overall, DALI processed meat products provide a uniform flavor experienced. (Sa kabuuan, ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay nagbibigay ng pantay-pantay na karanasan sa lasa.)	3.61	0.51	Highly Preferred
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.56	0.36	Highly Preferred
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Highly Preferred (HP), 1.75 – 2.49 Less Preferred (LP),	2.50 – 3.24 Preferred (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Preferred (NP)	

Table 2.2 showed that DALI processed meat products were highly preferred for flavor, with a mean rating of 3.56. The highest agreement was for flavor consistency across bites (mean 3.67), highlighting the importance of uniform taste in building customer trust and loyalty. The lowest rating, still high at 3.46, indicated slight but occasional flavor variation.

Robinson (2025) supported these findings, emphasizing that flavor consistency promotes satisfaction and repeat purchases. Hassoun et al. (2022) noted that sensory reliability is crucial for consumer acceptance, and DALI's consistent flavor helps build trust and emotional connection. Pallada (2025) also pointed out that consistent taste and freshness are key to lasting customer relationships. The respondents suggested the development of additional product types and recommended the introduction of new flavors for existing processed meat products. Overall, reliable flavor quality in DALI products encourages trust, loyalty, and repeat purchasing.

Table 2.3
Level of Preferences among Customers on DALI Processed Meat Products in Terms of Packaging Consistency.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. The packaging materials used for DALI processed meat products are consistently of high quality. (Ang mga materyales na ginagamit sa packaging ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay palaging may mataas na kalidad.)	3.60	0.50	Highly Preferred
2. The packaging size and portioning of DALI processed meat products are consistent across purchases. (Ang laki at hati ng packaging ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay palaging pare-pareho sa bawat pagbili.)	3.54	0.54	Highly Preferred
3. The packaging color and branding of DALI processed meat products are consistently applied. (Ang kulay at tatak ng packaging ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay palaging maayos at pare-pareho ang pagkakagamit.)	3.57	0.52	Highly Preferred
4. The packaging of DALI processed meat products protects the product from damage or contamination. (Ang packaging ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay palaging nakakapagprotekta sa produkto laban sa pinsala o kontaminasyon.)	3.63	0.51	Highly Preferred
5. Overall, the packaging of DALI processed meat products is consistent and reliable. (Sa kabuuan, ang packaging ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay pare-pareho at maaasahan.)	3.79	0.42	Highly Preferred
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.63	0.36	Highly Preferred
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Highly Preferred (HP), 1.75 – 2.49 Less Preferred (LP),	2.50 – 3.24 Preferred (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Preferred (NP)	

Table 2.3 showed that DALI processed meat products were highly preferred for packaging consistency, with a mean rating of 3.63. The highest agreement was for overall packaging reliability (mean 3.79), while packaging size and portioning had the lowest, yet

still high, mean of 3.54. This indicates strong consumer confidence in DALI's packaging quality and safety.

Innovation Market Insights (2025) supported these findings, stressing that modern packaging should communicate sustainability, safety, and professionalism. Garmyn (2020) also noted that packaging and appearance greatly influence consumer preferences by enhancing product credibility and brand recognition. Hassoun et al. (2022) further emphasized the importance of consistency, not just in flavor but also in packaging, as key to consumer acceptance and satisfaction. Overall, reliable and professional packaging strengthens consumer trust, satisfaction, and repeat purchase behavior.

Table 2.4
Level of Preferences among Customers on DALI Processed Meat Products in Terms of Presentation.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. The overall presentation of DALI processed meat products is visually appealing. (Ang pangkalahatang presentasyon ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay kaaya-aya sa paningin.)	3.61	0.52	Highly Preferred
2. The color of DALI processed meat products looks fresh and appetizing. (Ang kulay ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay mukhang sariwa at nakakatakam.)	3.59	0.52	Highly Preferred
3. The product slices or portions of DALI processed meat products are presented uniformly. (Ang bawat hiwa o hati ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay parepareho.)	3.50	0.54	Highly Preferred
4. The presentation of DALI processed meat products increases my willingness to purchase them. (Ang presentasyon ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay nakadaragdag sa aking kagustuhang bilhin ang mga ito.)	3.55	0.53	Highly Preferred
5. Overall, the presentation of DALI processed meat products meets my expectations. (Sa kabuuan, ang presentasyon ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay tugma sa aking inaasahan.)	3.57	0.50	Highly Preferred
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.56	0.38	Highly Preferred
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Highly Preferred (HP), 1.75 – 2.49 Less Preferred (LP),	2.50 – 3.24 Preferred (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Preferred (NP)	

Table 2.4 showed that DALI processed meat products were highly preferred for presentation, with an overall mean of 3.56. The highest rating was for visual appeal (mean 3.61), while uniformity of slices had the lowest, though still positive, mean of 3.50. This suggests customers find DALI products visually appealing and fresh-looking, but see room for slight improvement in portion consistency.

Zhao et al. (2021) found that appealing packaging and information significantly influence buying behavior by enhancing satisfaction. Shukla et al. (2022) emphasized

that creative and relevant presentation, such as DALI's uniform slices and appetizing color, increases curiosity and purchase intention. Andrea Garmyn (2020) also highlighted that appearance and packaging are key to consumer preferences. Overall, the attractive and consistent presentation of DALI products helps drive consumer trust and purchase decisions.

Table 2.5
Level of Preferences among Customers on DALI Processed Meat Products in Terms of Product Freshness.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I prefer DALI processed meat products that show natural freshness in their appearance and quality. (Mas gusto ko ang mga prosesong karne ng DALI na malinaw na nagpapakita ng natural na kasariwaan sa hitsura at kalidad ng produkto.)	3.64	0.51	Highly Preferred
2. I enjoy DALI processed meat products that smell clean and fresh when opened. (Nasisiyahan ako sa mga prosesong karne ng DALI dahil sa amoy nito na malinis at sariwa kapag binuksan.)	3.57	0.53	Highly Preferred
3. I prefer buying DALI processed meat products that give the impression of being freshly made. (Mas gusto kong bumili ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI na sa aking pakiramdam ay bagong gawa.)	3.56	0.54	Highly Preferred
4. I appreciate DALI processed meat products packaging that helps keep the product fresh longer. (Na-appreciate ko ang packaging ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil nakakatulong ito upang magtagal na sariwa ang mga produkto.)	3.55	0.54	Highly Preferred
5. I want DALI processed meat to be consistently fresh every time I buy it. (Nais ko na ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay palaging sariwa sa bawat aking pagbili.)	3.62	0.54	Highly Preferred
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.59	0.37	Highly Preferred
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Highly Preferred (HP), 1.75 – 2.49 Less Preferred (LP),	2.50 – 3.24 Preferred (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Preferred (NP)	

Table 2.5 showed that DALI processed meat products were highly preferred for freshness, with an overall mean of 3.59. The highest rating was for natural freshness in appearance and quality (mean 3.64), while packaging's role in maintaining freshness received a slightly lower, but still positive, mean of 3.55. This indicates customers strongly value inherent product freshness, with packaging seen as supportive.

Min et al. (2023) emphasized that freshness is a key driver of satisfaction and repeat purchases. Lano et al. (2025) found that consumers rank freshness and quality as top market preferences, which aligns with the high ratings for DALI's products. Mehta et al. (2024) noted that packaging color, material, and labeling shape perceptions of freshness, further reinforcing customer trust and confidence. Overall, the consistent freshness of DALI products enhances satisfaction, loyalty, and competitive advantage.

Table 2.6
Level of Preferences among Customers on DALI Processed Meat Products in Terms of Shelf Life.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Shelf-life information strongly influences my decision to purchase DALI processed meat products. (Ang nakasaad na shelf life ay nagbibigay ng gabay sa aking desisyon sa pagbili ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI.)	3.77	0.47	Highly Preferred
2. The expiration or “best before” dates on DALI processed meat products are clear and easy to understand. (Ang expiration o “best before” dates ng mga prosesong karne ng DALI ay malinaw at madaling maintindihan.)	3.61	0.54	Highly Preferred
3. A longer shelf life of DALI processed meat products would increase my likelihood of purchasing them. (Ang mas mahabang shelf life ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay makadaragdag sa aking kagustuhang bilhin ang mga ito.)	3.61	0.52	Highly Preferred
4. I am more likely to recommend DALI products because of their dependable shelf life. (Mas gusto ko na irekomenda ko ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil sa kanilang maaasahang shelf life.)	3.57	0.54	Highly Preferred
5. My satisfaction with DALI processed meat products is strongly influenced by their shelf life. (Malaki ang naging impluwensya ng shelf life sa aking kasiyahan sa mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI.)	3.64	0.51	Highly Preferred
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.64	0.37	Highly Preferred
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Highly Preferred (HP), 1.75 – 2.49 Less Preferred (LP),	2.50 – 3.24 Preferred (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Preferred (NP)	

Table 2.6 showed that shelf life is highly preferred among DALI processed meat consumers, with an overall mean of 3.64. The highest mean (3.77) was for the influence of shelf life information on purchase decisions, while recommending DALI products due to shelf life had a slightly lower mean of 3.57, though still positive. This demonstrates that clear and dependable shelf life is important for customer satisfaction and confidence in product safety.

Siddiqui et al. (2022) emphasized shelf life as a critical factor in consumer acceptance, especially for meat products, supporting the survey’s focus on expiration dates and clear labeling. Ntzimani (2025) highlighted the role of advanced packaging and testing in ensuring product safety, aligning with customers’ appreciation for reliable shelf-life information. Shukla (2025) explained that dependable shelf life helps meet or exceed consumer expectations, fostering satisfaction and loyalty. Overall, both the findings and literature confirm that shelf life is vital for building consumer trust, brand credibility, and competitiveness, with clear labeling and reliable expiration dates being essential for DALI’s market success.

Table 2.7
Level of Preferences among Customers on DALI Processed Meat Products in Terms of Texture, Appearance, and Physical Quality.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. The texture of DALI processed meat products I purchase is consistent and meets my expectations. (Ang tekstura ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI na aking binibili ay palaging tugma sa aking inaasahan.)	3.59	0.54	Highly Preferred
2. The DALI processed meat products I purchase have an appetizing aroma. (Ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI na aking binibili ay may nakakatakam na amoy.)	3.53	0.54	Highly Preferred
3. The overall presentation and packaging of DALI processed meat products enhance their appearance and perceived quality. (Ang pangkalahatang presentasyon at packaging ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay nagpapaganda ng kanilang anyo at kalidad.)	3.57	0.54	Highly Preferred
4. I am satisfied with the tenderness of DALI processed meat products. (Ako ay nasisiyahan sa lambot ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI.)	3.55	0.52	Highly Preferred
5. I am generally satisfied with the texture, appearance, and physical quality of DALI processed meat products available in local stores. (Sa pangkalahatan, ako ay nasisiyahan sa tekstura, anyo, at pisikal na kalidad ng mga prosesong karne ng DALI na mabibili sa mga lokal na tindahan.)	3.59	0.51	Highly Preferred
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.57	0.40	Highly Preferred
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Highly Preferred (HP), 1.75 – 2.49 Less Preferred (LP),	2.50 – 3.24 Preferred (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Preferred (NP)	

Table 2.7 showed that DALI processed meat products were highly preferred for texture, appearance, and physical quality, with an overall mean of 3.56. The highest mean was for overall satisfaction with these attributes (3.59), while aroma received a slightly lower but still positive mean of 3.53. This indicates that customers value the products' sensory and visual qualities, with a particular emphasis on texture and appearance.

Sheng et al. (2025) found that aroma and aftertaste are key drivers of purchase intent, which is supported by respondents' strong agreement on DALI's appealing aroma and texture. Liu et al. (2025) highlighted the importance of tenderness and mouthfeel, aligning with high satisfaction ratings for these attributes. Lapčik et al. (2025) noted that modern processing and packaging techniques preserve sensory integrity and enhance perceived quality, which respondents confirmed by valuing DALI's packaging and presentation. Overall, strong sensory and physical qualities lead to higher customer satisfaction and repeat purchases.

Table 2.8
Level of Preferences among Customers on DALI Processed Meat Products in
Terms of Availability and Reliability of Supply.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. The supply of DALI processed meat products in my area is consistent and reliable. (Ang suplay ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI sa aming lugar ay palaging pare-pareho at maaasahan.)	3.76	0.47	Highly Preferred
2. I am satisfied with the frequency of restocking of DALI processed meat products in stores. (Ako ay nasisiyahan sa dalas ng pagre-restock ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI sa mga tindahan.)	3.61	0.53	Highly Preferred
3. The availability of DALI processed meat products meets the demand of consumers in my community. (Ang pagkakaroon ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay tumutugon sa pangangailangan ng mga mamimili sa aking komunidad.)	3.63	0.51	Highly Preferred
4. Seasonal demand does not significantly affect the availability of DALI processed meat products. (Ang pana-panahong demand ay hindi gaanong nakakaapekto sa pagiging available ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI.)	3.43	0.55	Highly Preferred
5. Overall, I am satisfied with the availability and reliability of the supply of DALI processed meat products in local markets. (Sa kabuuan, ako ay nasisiyahan sa pagkakaroon at pagiging maaasahan ng suplay ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI sa mga lokal na pamilihan.)	3.59	0.53	Highly Preferred
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.61	0.37	Highly Preferred
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Highly Preferred (HP), 1.75 – 2.49 Less Preferred (LP),	2.50 – 3.24 Preferred (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Preferred (NP)	

Table 2.8 showed that the availability and reliability of supply for DALI processed meat products were highly preferred, with an overall mean of 3.61. The highest mean was for consistent and reliable supply (3.76), while product availability during seasonal demand received a slightly lower, but still positive, mean of 3.43. This indicates customers generally view DALI's supply chain as dependable, though some fluctuations may occur during peak periods.

Larson (2024) emphasized the importance of strong inventory management for product availability and consumer trust, supporting the survey's findings of reliable supply. Kumar (2025) highlighted that technological advancements and automation improve efficiency and product availability, aligning with customers' appreciation for frequent restocking. Pallada (2025) noted that consistent availability builds trust and loyalty. Overall, steady supply and reliable inventory systems are crucial for customer satisfaction, trust, and brand competitiveness in the local market.

Table 3.1
Level of customer buying behavior among customers of Dali processed meat products in terms of Frequency of Purchase.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I buy DALI-processed meat products frequently for their consistent quality. (Madalas akong bumibili ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil sa kanilang palagiang kalidad.)	3.66	0.52	Very High
2. I buy DALI processed meat products frequently because they are more affordable than other brands. (Madalas akong bumili ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil mas abot-kaya ang halaga nito kumpara sa ibang brand.)	3.57	0.55	Very High
3. I repurchase DALI processed meat products because they are always readily available in their store. (Ako ay palaging bumibili ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil palagi itong available sa kanilang tindahan.)	3.57	0.55	Very High
4. I repurchase DALI processed meat products because they fit my household's food preferences. (Ako ay bibiling muli ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil akma sila sa kagustuhan sa pagkain ng aking pamilya.)	3.48	0.54	Very High
5. I repurchase DALI processed meat products because I prefer their taste. (Ako ay bibiling muli ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil mas gusto ko ang lasa ng mga ito.)	3.59	0.54	Very High
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.57	0.57	Very High
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Very High (VH), 1.75 – 2.49 Low (L),	2.50 – 3.24 High (H) 1.00 – 1.74 Very Low (VL)	

Table 3.1 showed a very high frequency of purchase for DALI processed meat products, with an overall mean of 3.57. The highest mean (3.66) was for purchases driven by consistent quality, while household food preferences had a slightly lower mean (3.48), though still positive. This indicates that reliability in quality and affordability are the main motivators for frequent repurchasing.

Libiran et al. (2023) supported these findings, linking repeat purchases to customer satisfaction with flavor, freshness, packaging, and availability. Teixeira et al. (2024) emphasized that taste, freshness, and competitive pricing are key to loyalty and repeat buying. Mamuaya (2024) also found that product quality, brand reputation, and affordability sustain high purchase frequency. Overall, the results highlight that dependable quality and accessible pricing are crucial for driving loyalty and repeat purchases among DALI customers.

Table 3.2
Level of customer buying behavior among customers of Dali processed meat products in terms of Brand Loyalty.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. My loyalty to DALI products is strongly influenced by my preference for their product quality compared to other brands. (Ang aking katapatan sa mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay malaki ang impluwensya mula sa aking kagustuhan sa kanilang kalidad kumpara sa ibang brand.)	3.58	0.57	Very High
2. My positive experiences with DALI-processed meat products strengthen my loyalty to the brand. (Ang aking patuloy na magagandang karanasan sa pagbili ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay nagiging dahilan ng mas matatag na katapatan/ pagtangkilik ko sa kanilang brand.)	3.57	0.55	Very High
3. I prefer to repurchase DALI processed meat products because I trust their quality. (Mas gusto kong palagiang bumili ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil may tiwala ako sa kanilang kalidad.)	3.59	0.54	Very High
4. I am less likely to switch to another brand once I find one that meets my expectations. (Hindi ako madaling lumipat sa ibang brand kapag nakahanap ako ng isa na tumutugon sa aking inaasahan.)	3.53	0.56	Very High
5. Overall, my loyalty to a specific brand determines how often I repurchase DALI processed meat products. (Sa kabuuan, ang aking katapatan sa isang partikular na brand ang nagtatakda kung gaano kadalas akong bumili ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI)	3.78	0.57	Very High
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.61	0.57	Very High
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Very High (VH), 1.75 – 2.49 Low (L),	2.50 – 3.24 High (H) 1.00 – 1.74 Very Low (VL)	

Table 3.2 showed a very high level of brand loyalty for DALI processed meat products, with an overall mean of 3.61. The highest mean (3.78) was for brand loyalty driving repurchase frequency, while reluctance to switch brands had a slightly lower mean (3.53), indicating that although most customers are loyal, some may consider alternatives if expectations are not met.

Cardoso (2022) supported these findings by highlighting that brand loyalty is built on trust and consistent product quality. Sulistia (2022) emphasized that emotional engagement with the brand strengthens loyalty and encourages continued repurchasing. Rahehagh (2021) added that emotional attachment makes customers more resilient to competitors and price changes. Overall, maintaining high product quality, building emotional connections, and reinforcing trust are key to sustaining strong brand loyalty and repeat purchases for DALI in the local market.

Table 3.3
Level of customer buying behavior among customers of Dali processed meat products in terms of Product Choice.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I repurchase DALI processed meat products because they consistently meet my taste preferences. (Ako ay palagiang bumibili ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil ito ay patuloy na tumutugma sa aking nais na lasa.)	3.58	0.54	Very High
2. I choose DALI processed meat products over competitors because of their affordability and product quality. (Pinipili ko ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI kaysa sa mga kakumpitensya dahil sa kanilang pagiging abot-kaya at kalidad ng produkto.)	3.58	0.56	Very High
3. I always chose DALI processed meat products because they suited my cooking or meal-preparation needs. (Palagi kong pinipili ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil akma sila sa aking pangangailangan sa pagluluto o paghahanda ng pagkain.)	3.53	0.56	Very High
4. My choice of DALI processed meat products is strongly influenced by my preference for this brand over other brands. (Mas pinipili ko ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil mas gusto ko talaga ang brand na ito kumpara sa iba.)	3.58	0.57	Very High
5. I continue to buy DALI processed meat products because their taste always satisfies me. (Patuloy akong bumibili ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil palagi akong nasisiyahan sa kanilang lasa.)	3.56	0.56	Very High
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.56	0.42	Very High

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Very High (VH), 2.50 – 3.24 High (H)
 1.75 – 2.49 Low (L), 1.00 – 1.74 Very Low (VL)

Table 3.3 showed a very high level of product choice for DALI processed meat products, with an overall mean of 3.56. The highest mean (3.58) was for brand preference influencing product choice, while suitability for cooking had a slightly lower mean (3.53). This indicates that taste, affordability, and brand preference are the main reasons customers consistently choose DALI products, with cooking suitability also valued.

Yue et al. (2024) emphasized that taste, texture, and freshness are the top factors in consumer selection of processed meats, aligning with the survey’s findings. de Araujo et al. (2022) noted that affordability and freshness often outweigh brand name in purchasing decisions, which matches the strong preference for DALI’s pricing and quality. Garmyn (2020) highlighted the importance of both extrinsic cues, such as price and packaging, and intrinsic qualities such as flavor and tenderness. Overall, maintaining high product quality, affordability, and suitability for household needs is crucial for DALI to reinforce trust, brand loyalty, and repeat purchases in the local market.

Table 3.4
Level of customer buying behavior among customers of Dali processed meat products in terms of Willingness to Recommend.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am willing to recommend DALI processed meat products because of their affordable price. (Handa akong irekomenda ang mga prosesong karne ng DALI dahil sa kanilang abot-kayang presyo.)	3.63	0.52	Very High
2. I am willing to recommend DALI processed meat products because of their good product quality. (Handa akong irekomenda ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil sa magandang kalidad ng kanilang produkto.)	3.58	0.52	Very High
3. I am willing to recommend DALI processed meat products because of their unconditional return policy for products that do not meet customers' expectations. (Handa akong irekomenda ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil sa kanilang walang kondisyong patakaran sa pagbabalik ng produkto na hindi nakatugon sa inaasahan ng mga mamimili.)	3.63	0.52	Very High
4. I am willing to recommend DALI processed meat products because the expiration or "best before" dates on DALI processed meat products are clear and easy to understand. (Handa akong irekomenda ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil malinaw at madaling maintindihan ang mga petsa ng pagkapaso o 'best before' na nakalagay sa kanilang mga produkto.)	3.64	0.51	Very High
5. I am willing to recommend DALI processed meat products due to their reliable availability. (Handa akong irekomenda ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil laging available at madaling hanapin ang mga ito.)	3.62	0.52	Very High
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.62	0.36	Very High
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Very High (VH), 1.75 – 2.49 Low (L),	2.50 – 3.24 High (H) 1.00 – 1.74 Very Low (VL)	

Table 3.4 showed a very high willingness to recommend DALI processed meat products, with an overall mean of 3.62. The highest mean (3.64) was for clear and understandable expiration dates, while product quality as a reason for recommendation had a slightly lower mean (3.58). This indicates that affordability, reliable availability, product quality, and especially transparent labeling strongly encourage customers to recommend DALI products.

Shukla (2025) supported this, emphasizing that satisfaction and recommendations are driven by the match between expectations and actual product performance, particularly clear labeling and dependable quality. Larson (2024) highlighted the importance of consistent availability and inventory management in building

trust and loyalty. Pallada (2025) argued that quality, freshness, and transparency are key to lasting customer relationships. Overall, willingness to recommend DALI products is driven by a combination of product quality, affordability, transparency, and reliable supply.

Table 3.5
Level of customer buying behavior among customers of Dali processed meat products in terms of Emotional Connection to the Brand.

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I feel a strong connection to DALI processed meat products because they suit my taste preferences. (Malapit ang loob ko sa mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil tumutugma sila sa aking mga panlasa.)	3.50	0.56	Very High
2. I feel a sense of satisfaction when I repurchase DALI processed meat products. (Nakakaramdam ako ng kasiyahan kapag nabili ako ng mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI.)	3.55	0.53	Very High
3. I confidently recommend DALI processed meat products because of my positive experiences with them. (Kumpiyansa ako na irekomenda ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI dahil sa aking mga positibong karanasan sa kanilang produkto.)	3.51	0.56	Very High
4. I feel that DALI processed meat products are part of my household's food identity. (Nararamdaman ko na ang mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay bahagi ng pagkakakilanlan sa pagkain ng aking pamilya.)	3.49	0.57	Very High
5. My emotional connection to DALI processed meat products, based on my product preferences, motivates me to repurchase their products regularly. (Ang aking emosyonal na pagkakaugnay sa mga prosesong produkto na karne ng DALI ay batay sa aking mga kagustuhan sa produkto, ay nag-uudyok sa aking palagiang pagbili ng kanilang mga produkto.)	3.54	0.54	Very High
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.51	0.46	Very High
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Very High (VH), 1.75 – 2.49 Low (L),	2.50 – 3.24 High (H) 1.00 – 1.74 Very Low (VL)	

Table 3.5 showed a very high emotional connection to the DALI brand, with an overall mean of 3.51. The highest mean (3.55) was for satisfaction gained from repurchasing, while DALI products as part of household food identity had a slightly lower mean (3.49). This indicates that emotional fulfillment and trust in product quality are major factors driving loyalty and repeat purchases.

Sulistia (2022) emphasized the importance of emotional engagement in building long-term loyalty, which aligns with these findings. Libiran et al. (2023) found that repeat purchases are closely linked to customer satisfaction with factors like flavor, freshness, and availability. Rahehagh (2021) noted that emotional attachment turns satisfied buyers into committed brand advocates. Overall, strong emotional bonds, alongside consistent

product quality, are essential for sustaining customer loyalty and trust in DALI processed meat products.

4. The significant relationship between customer preferences and buying behavior.

The results of the Spearman's rho correlation and regression analyses showed a significant positive relationship between customer preferences and buying behavior toward DALI processed meat products. All preference variables, including taste, flavor, packaging, presentation, freshness, shelf life, texture/appearance, and availability/reliability, were positively correlated with buying behavior indicators such as purchase frequency, brand loyalty, product choice, recommendation, and emotional connection, with all correlations significant at the 0.01 level. Taste was strongly linked to brand loyalty ($r = .515$) and product choice ($r = .516$), while flavor correlated highly with freshness ($r = .587$) and product choice ($r = .567$). Packaging and presentation also showed moderate to strong correlations with loyalty and recommendation ($r = .476$ to $.569$). Freshness emerged as especially influential, correlating highly with product choice ($r = .600$) and recommendation ($r = .537$).

Regression analysis reinforced these findings, with preference variables explaining 61.5% ($R^2 = .615$) of the variance in brand loyalty. The strongest predictors of loyalty were availability/reliability and texture/appearance, followed by taste, packaging, and freshness. Product choice was most influenced by freshness, shelf life, presentation, and flavor, while recommendation was driven by shelf life, availability, and freshness. Emotional connection was best predicted by freshness, availability, and texture/appearance. In summary, customer preferences, especially those related to taste, freshness, packaging, and supply reliability, play a critical role in shaping and enhancing consumer loyalty, repeat purchases, and emotional connection to the DALI brand.

5. Influence of Customer Preferences on Buying Behavior.

The study's correlation and regression analyses demonstrated that customer preferences, including taste, flavor, packaging, presentation, freshness, shelf life, texture/appearance, and availability, significantly and positively influenced buying behavior indicators such as purchase frequency, brand loyalty, product choice, recommendation, and emotional connection. Taste was strongly associated with brand loyalty ($r = .515$) and product choice ($r = .516$), supporting findings by Hong et al. (2023), de Araujo et al. (2022), and Sheng et al. (2025) that taste and freshness are decisive factors in purchasing decisions. Flavor also showed high correlations with freshness ($r = .587$) and product choice ($r = .567$), echoing Robinson (2025), Hassoun et al. (2022), and Pallada (2025) that consistent flavor and quality promote trust and repeat purchases. Packaging and presentation correlated moderately to strongly with loyalty and recommendation ($r = .476$ – $.569$), as highlighted by Zhao et al. (2021) and Shukla et al. (2022), who found that creative packaging and clear product information boost trust and purchase intentions.

Freshness was one of the most influential factors, linked to product choice ($r = .600$) and recommendation ($r = .537$). This supports Min et al. (2023), Lano et al. (2025),

and Mehta et al. (2024), who emphasized freshness as a critical driver of satisfaction and loyalty. Shelf life also showed important associations with product choice ($r = .532$) and recommendation ($r = .538$), consistent with Siddiqui et al. (2022) and Shukla (2025), who noted that dependable shelf life fosters confidence and repeat purchases. Ultimately, availability and reliability of supply were strongly linked to brand loyalty ($r = .581$) and emotional connection ($r = .441$), as supported by Larson (2024), Kumar (2025), and Pallada (2025), who stressed the importance of robust inventory and supply chain management for customer satisfaction and trust. Overall, the findings confirm that improvements in product attributes directly enhance loyalty, satisfaction, and emotional connection to the DALI brand.

6. Strategic recommendations can be developed to improve customer preference and buying behavior toward DALI processed meat products.

Based on the findings of the study, several strategic recommendations can be developed to improve customer preference and buying behavior toward DALI processed meat products. These action plan recommendations are based on the results of the collected data of the study. In this regard, the following strategies are proposed:

Table 6.1 Action Plan for DALI Processed Meat Products

Strategic Area	Objective	Actions	Timeline	Responsible Units	Estimated Budget Allocation	Success Indicators
1. Continuous New Product Development	Sustain consumer interest and strengthen competitiveness through innovations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop new processed meat product lines. Introduce additional flavor variants for existing products 	Continuous	Product Development, R&D, Marketing	₱2M annually (R&D, product testing, market launch)	≥2 new product launches per year; ≥80% positive consumer acceptance; 10% increase in market share
2. Taste & Flavor Consistency	Guarantee uniform taste across all batches to sustain consumer trust.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuous, stricter quality control protocols with batch testing. 	Continuous	Quality Assurance, Purchasing	₱300,000 annually (QC equipment)	≥95% batch compliance in sensory tests; <5% consumer complaints on taste
3. Freshness & Shelf Life	Ensure product integrity and sustainability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invest in cold-chain logistics. Adopt eco-friendly packaging technologies. 	Continuous	Supply Chain, Logistics, Purchasing	₱1M initial investment + ₱100,000 annual maintenance	Shelf life extended by 20%; <2% spoilage returns
4. Availability & Reliability of Supply (ARS)	Prevent stock-outs and reinforce brand dependability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consistent inventory monitoring systems. Strengthen distribution partnerships. 	Continuous	Operations, Sales & Logistics	₱800,000 (software maintenance + training)	Stock-out rate <3%; ≥95% on-time replenishment

5. Emotional Connection & Brand Loyalty	Build deeper consumer relationships beyond transactions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch loyalty programs. • Maintain interactive digital campaigns. 	Continuous Short-term (6 months)	Marketing, Customer Relations	₱500,000 (loyalty system)	Loyalty program enrollment ≥10,000; Engagement rate ≥15% on digital platforms
6. Demographic-Specific Strategies	Tailor promotions to consumer segments.	Continuous developing premium eco-friendly lines and transparency cues.	Quarterly adjustment depends on customers' needs	Marketing, Operations & Sales	₱1.5M annually (segmented campaigns)	Segment-specific sales growth ≥10%; Campaign recall ≥70%
7. Integration and Monitoring	Ensure cohesive implementation and continuous improvement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set KPIs (repeat purchase rate, brand loyalty index, etc.). • Conduct quarterly reviews. 	Continuous	Operation, Sales, Marketing & Purchasing	₱300,000 annually (task force operations, KPI tracking tools)	Quarterly KPI achievement ≥80%; Continuous improvement documented

Conclusions

The study's conclusions, which were based on the information gathered and the responses collected throughout the research, were presented in this section. The conclusions provided a logical overview of the findings in relation to the study's objectives and demonstrated how the data supported the results.

- 1. Demographic influence.** Age, gender, marital status, religion, education, and income all influenced DALI processed meat product preferences. Young adults, singles, and high school graduates formed the main consumer base, and they prioritized affordability, taste, and convenience.
- 2. Positive preferences.** Customers had strong positive preferences for DALI products. They valued taste, packaging, freshness, and consistent quality, while also expressing a desire for greater product variety.
- 3. Purchase drivers.** Frequent purchases were driven by affordability and taste, particularly among younger and middle-income consumers. These groups demonstrated strong brand loyalty and were likely to recommend DALI products.
- 4. Behavioral factors.** Sensory attributes and affordability significantly influenced buying behavior. Customer satisfaction drove loyalty and recommendations, making preferences key predictors of consumer actions.
- 5. Main purchase drivers.** Taste and affordability were the primary drivers of purchase frequency and brand loyalty, especially among younger and lower-income groups. Satisfaction was directly linked to repeat buying.
- 6. Recommendations.** Recommendations included maintaining taste consistency, offering healthier options, enhancing packaging transparency, tailoring marketing strategies by segment, keeping products affordable, and leveraging cultural values to strengthen loyalty and market presence.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations were made to improve product development, marketing methods, and future research direction.

- 1. Consistency of product quality, affordability, taste, and the transparency system.** Consistent quality, built consumer trust, and reinforced reliability, which encouraged repeat purchases. DALI's price affordability enabled it to maintain competitiveness in the Calamba City market. Consistency in taste and flavor emerged as the primary factors influencing loyalty, requiring continuous evaluation for uniqueness. Ultimately, transparent nutritional labeling responded to increasing customer demand for accountability and health-oriented options, establishing DALI as a reliable and trustworthy brand. Together, these components established the basis for maintaining customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, and enduring competitiveness.
- 2. Loyalty programs, bundle deals, and discounts.** The loyalty programs, bundle deals, and discounts DALI can encourage frequent purchases, especially among younger and lower-income consumers. Emotional connection should be built through relatable advertising and community engagement, while product diversification will sustain loyalty across different consumer segments.
- 3. Consistency of product research and development system.** DALI should introduce healthier product variants without compromising flavor and quality standards. And also, continuous development of additional product types and new flavors for existing processed meat products.
- 4. Implementing effective inventory monitoring systems.** DALI should strengthen product availability and reliability by implementing effective inventory monitoring systems to minimize stock-outs and ensure timely replenishment. Consistent accessibility will reinforce consumer trust, prevent preference shifts to competitors, and encourage repeat purchases.
- 5. Continuous customer feedback and recommendations system.** DALI should consider a continuous customer feedback and recommendations system because customers actively share their experiences and suggestions with DALI processed meat products, as consumer feedback plays a vital role in improving product quality, enhancing satisfaction, and fostering stronger emotional connections with the brand.
- 6. Adopting the proposed strategic recommendations.** DALI may consider adopting the proposed strategic recommendations to enhance both customer acquisition and retention, given that these strategies are informed by empirical evidence derived from the voice of the market.
- 7. Future researchers** are encouraged to explore emerging factors like sustainability, ethical sourcing, and digital marketing, as these are increasingly influencing consumer behavior. Longitudinal studies could track changes in preferences and buying habits over time, particularly as younger consumers get older. Also, using qualitative methods such as focus groups or interviews may offer a deeper understanding of emotional and cultural influences that surveys might miss. Comparative studies across different regions or brands would also help

determine if the findings from Calamba apply more broadly, thus enhancing the generalizability of the results.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study upheld the highest standards of ethical research throughout all stages of data collection and analysis. In conducting this study, strict adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173) was observed to protect the confidentiality and integrity of respondent information. The law emphasized transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality in the collection and processing of personal data, ensuring that individuals' rights to privacy were safeguarded. Respondents' socio-economic and demographic details were collected solely for academic purposes, with informed consent obtained before participation. Data were anonymized and securely stored to prevent unauthorized access, in compliance with the standards set by the National Privacy Commission. As highlighted in the Act, "the State recognizes the vital role of information and communications technology in nation-building and its inherent obligation to ensure that personal information in information and communications systems in the government and in the private sector are secured and protected" (2012).

At the University of Cabuyao, research was treated as both an academic pursuit and a moral responsibility. To uphold this principle, the Research Ethics Review Committee (RERC) reviewed all proposals to ensure integrity, respect, and accountability. Ethical clearance was required before any data collection, with researchers submitting proposals, consent forms, and risk assessments for approval. The policy was guided by universal principles of respect for persons, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice, while aligning with CHED, DOST, and international standards such as the Belmont Report. In this way, the university embedded ethical responsibility into its culture, reminding students and faculty that they must always protect human dignity and promote trust.

The following ethical principles guided the conduct of the research:

- 1. Informed Consent:** All respondents were fully informed about the nature, objectives, and procedures of the study before participation. Written or verbal consent was obtained from each participant, ensuring they understood that their involvement was voluntary and that they could withdraw at any time without penalty.
- 2. Confidentiality and Anonymity:** The privacy of respondents was strictly protected. No personal identifiers were collected, and all responses were treated as confidential. Data was reported in aggregate form only, ensuring that individual participants could not be identified in any publication or report.
- 3. Non-Maleficence:** The study was designed and conducted to avoid causing any harm or discomfort to participants. The questions are framed respectfully and sensitively, and respondents will not be subjected to any risks or undue pressure.

4. **Data Protection:** All survey data was securely stored and accessible only to the research team. The electronic data was password-protected, and physical documents were kept in a secure location to prevent unauthorized access.
5. **Integrity and Objectivity:** Maintained the researcher's objectivity and integrity in data collection, analysis, and reporting. Any potential conflicts of interest were disclosed, and findings were presented honestly and without fabrication or misrepresentation.

By adhering to these ethical guidelines, the study ensures the rights, dignity, and well-being of all participants, while also maintaining the credibility and reliability of the research findings.

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